

SURVEILLANCE CARD: Q-Fever -Indicator-based surveillance of abortions in ruminants, followed by pathogen detection in aborted fetuses

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Indicator-based surveillance of abortions in all domestic ruminants, followed by antigen testing for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> in farms with high incidence.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of an increase in incidence, i.e., early epidemic detection.
3	Target species and group	Sheep, goats and cattle, adult breeding females.
4	Target sector / production type	All production types.
5	Geographical area covered	All regions.
6	Age group	Adult females.
7	Sampling point and strategy	On farm, testing of aborted foetuses in farms exceeding a certain incidence of abortions.
8	Sampling time period	Year round.
9	Sampling matrix	Tissue from aborted foetuses and birth material.
10	Type of disease indicators	Pathogen.
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal and farm.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Purposeful, selection of animals with abortion.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	PCR is the most reliable tool for diagnosis of (<i>C. burnetii</i>) infection-related abortions. For lab diagnosis in the context of serial abortions/stillbirths, samples should be collected from aborted fetuses, placenta and vaginal discharges soon after abortion or parturition. If possible, vaginal swabs at the day of abortion (or taken less than 8 days after) should be collected in order to limit the number of false-negative PCR results. The confirmation of clinical cases should always include a differential investigation of major abortive agents and target at least two aborted animals.

14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	This surveillance component is potentially highly sensitive, and also allows timely detection of increased incidence of abortions due to <i>C. burnetii</i> . However, this greatly depends on disease awareness, how well the animals are observed (in extensively kept sheep and goats, abortion often go unnoticed), and whether there are incentives to notify cases of abortions.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Rift Valley Fever, Brucellosis, Infectious Bovine Rhinotracheitis, Chlamydiosis (and many other pathogens causing abortions).
18	References	1) https://www.woah.org/en/disease/q-fever/ 2) Georgiev M, Afonso A, Neubauer H, Needham H, Thiéry R, Rodolakis A, Roest HJ, Stärk KD, Stegeman JA, Vellema P, van der Hoek W, More SJ. Q fever in humans and farm animals in four European countries, 1982 to 2010. Euro Surveill. 2013;18(8):pii=20407. Available online: http://www.eurosurveillance.org/ViewArticle.aspx?ArticleId=204073) De Crémoux, R., Gache, K., Rousset, E., Sala, C., Hosteing, S., Nicollet, P., ... & Touratier, A. (2018). A pilot program for clinical Q fever surveillance as a first step for a standardized differential diagnosis of abortions: Organizational lessons applied to goats farms. Small Ruminant Research, 163, 60-64. 4) Saegerman C, Grégoire F, Delooz L. Diagnosis of <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> Cattle Abortion: A One-Year Observational Study. Pathogens. 2022 Apr 1;11(4):429. doi: 10.3390/pathogens11040429. PMID: 35456104; PMCID: PMC9032501.

